

Isolation of Lupenone from *Cassia Siamea* Lam.

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From the light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the trunk-bark of *Cassia siamea* Lam. (Fam. Leguminosae) a neutral compound has been isolated. It crystallises from ethanol in needles, m.p. 170°, [α]_D²⁵ +67° (in CHCl₃). Its analysis corresponds to the molecular formula, C₃₀H₄₈O, which is in conformity with the mass-spectrometrically derived molecular weight, 424. The IR spectrum (5.9 μ) of the compound reveals the presence of a six-membered ring ketone system in the molecule and this is confirmed from its DNP derivative, crystallised from chloroform-methanol in needles, m.p. 205-207°. It develops a light pink colour with the Burchard-Lieberman reagent which suggests it to be a triterpenoid.

The above ketonic compound on sodium borohydride reduction furnishes an alcohol, C₃₀H₅₀O, crystallised from aqueous ethanol in needles, m.p. 211-12°, [α]_D²⁰ +28° (in CHCl₃). Complete identity of this compound with lupol has been established from mixed melting point determination and from superimposable IR spectra, thereby proving that the ketonic compound is lupenone. The mass fragmentation (m/e 205, 218, and 189) pattern is in full accord with that for lupenone¹.

Isolation of Lupenone.—Light petroleum extract (b.p. 60-80°) of the trunk-bark of *Cassia siamea* was treated with a 5% aqueous NaOH solution in order to separate the quinone compounds². The petroleum solution was then concentrated and chromatographed over deactivated alumina (Brockmann). The chromatogram on elution with benzene and benzene-chloroform mixture yielded lupenone. The ketonic compound was then repeatedly crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 170°. (Found: C, 84.56; H, 11.83. Calc. for C₃₀H₄₈O: C, 84.90; H, 11.32%).

DNP Derivative.—To a cooled methanolic solution of lupenone slightly acidic methanolic solution of dinitrophenylhydrazine was added. The reaction mixture on concentration and cooling furnished a beautiful yellow solid of the DNP derivative which was finally crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture in needles, m.p. 205-207°. (Found: C, 71.62; H, 8.82; N, 9.36. Calc. for C₂₆H₃₆O₄N₄: C, 71.52; H, 8.61; N, 9.27%).

Sodium Borohydride Reduction of Lupenone.—To a solution of lupenone (0.5 g.) in dry methanol was slowly added sodium borohydride (0.25 g.). The temperature was maintained at 10°. After final addition, the reaction mixture was kept overnight. Excess methanol was removed under suction; the product was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was worked up in the usual manner, when a solid substance was obtained, m.p. 208-209°, which was repeatedly crystallised from aqueous ethanol

1. Budzikiewicz *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3688.

2. Chatterjee and Bhattacharjee, *this Journal*, 1964, **41**, 415.

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to furnish lupeol, m.p. 211-12°. (Found: C 84.23; H. 11.85. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.35; H, 11.76%).

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